

Development of Experimental ECAP Extrusion Rig for Material Processing

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Abstract

Severe plastic deformation (SPD) methods over the years have become widely adopted for refining the grain structure of metallic materials thereby enhancing their mechanical properties. Amongst these methods, Equal Channel Angular PRESSING (ECAP) technique is the most popular possessing several advantages over the other SPD techniques. This research outlines the development of an experimental rig for equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) aimed at advancing material processing techniques. The rig components were designed using the Autodesk inventor software and materials selected were considered to meet research objectives. The fabrication process involved machining of procured workpiece to match the designs and dimensions derived from the virtual models. The experimental procedures incorporated multiple ECAP passes at varying temperatures (90, 100, 120, 140 and 150 degrees Celsius). The research contributes a robust and replicable experimental setup for ECAP with potential applications in optimizing material processing techniques for enhanced material properties.

Keywords—ECAP (equal channel angular pressing), extrusion rig design, experimental rig development, materials processing al-mg alloys, component design, materials extrusion.

INTRODUCTION

In the realm of materials engineering and manufacturing, advancements in processing techniques have a profound impact on the development of innovative materials and components. One of such techniques which has gained significant attention over the years is the equal channel angular pressing (ECAP), a severe plastic deformation technique used to refine grain structures and enhance material properties [1], [2], [3] and [4].

The successful implementation of ECAP relies not only on the unique deformation process but also the quality and precision of the extrusion rig used for materials processing. Therefore, the design and development of an extrusion rig has remained a pivotal role in the efficacy and feasibility of the entire process [5], [6] and [7]. This stems from the need to create a versatile and efficient tool for materials processing capable of handling a range of materials [8].

This study aims to develop an experimental ECAP extrusion rig, emphasizing its engineering specifications and implications for materials processing. Its objective is tailored towards enhancing the capabilities of ECAP processing thereby enabling researchers and manufacturers achieve greater control over materials properties and microstructure evolution [9], [10] and [11]. Furthermore, the ultimate aim is to contribute valuable insights and open new possibilities for advanced materials processing.

METHODOLOGY

A. Design Parameters

The design parameters employed include;

- **Magnitude of the shear strain**

The magnitude of the shear strain (γ) after a single pass in a frictionless condition is shown in Equation 1

$$\gamma = 2 \cot\left(\frac{\phi}{2} + \frac{\psi}{2}\right) + \psi \operatorname{cosec}\left(\frac{\phi}{2} + \frac{\psi}{2}\right) \quad (1)$$

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where (ϕ) is the die angle otherwise known as the die inner angle and (ψ), is the outer radius of curvature otherwise known as the channel fill

• **Total shear strain**

The total shear strain in the plastic deformation zone of the ECAP die assuming material velocity changes in direction is illustrated in equation 2

$$\epsilon = \frac{N}{\sqrt{3}} \left[2 \cot \left\{ \frac{\phi}{2} + \frac{\psi}{2} \right\} + \psi \operatorname{cosec} \left\{ \frac{\phi}{2} + \frac{\psi}{2} \right\} \right] \tag{2}$$

and if the outer radius of curvature be ignored (that is $\psi = 0$), then the total shear strain after a number of passes is illustrated in equation 3.

$$\epsilon = \frac{N}{\sqrt{3}} 2 \cot \phi \tag{3}$$

• **Punch Pressure**

The amount of pressure required for pressing is obtained using the equation 4.

$$P = t_0(1+m) \left[2 \cot \left(\frac{\phi+\psi}{2} \right) \right] + 4mt_0 \left(\frac{l_i+l_o}{a} \right) \tag{4}$$

Where, (t_0) is the shear strength, m is the friction coefficient, (l_i) is the sample length at channel entry, (l_o) is the sample length at exit channel, (a) is the area of the sample, N is the number of passes.

B. Design of Experimental ECAP Rig

The design of the experimental extrusion rig was a critical component of this research and was executed using the Autodesk inventor software. The key aspects of the rig design including components, materials and design specifications are outlined as follows;

• **Rig components**

The ECAP rig components was designed with precision. The plunger was created with dimensions 19.5 by 19.5 by 50 mm rectangular bar ensuring precise dimensions and geometric features that allow for controlled force application during the ECAP process.

Figure 1: (a)3D model of ECAP extrusion rig; (b) 2D Orthographic projection of extrusion rig.

The design of the rig was performed using the Autodesk Inventor resulting in a 3D model measuring 100 by 100 by 170 mm rectangular bar. Six fastener holes were bored and threaded through a distance of 45 mm ensuring secure assembly. Additionally, three 10 mm holes of depth 160mm were incorporated for purpose of heating elements as illustrated in figure 1. A hole of depth 15 mm and size 6 mm to accommodate a thermostat

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for temperature control was added. The rig was split into two. The Die, a critical part of the ECAP rig was designed allowing for the precise definition of the channel angle and dimensions to achieve the desired material deformation. The angle of curvature is 20° while the inner channel angle is 90° . The plunger and ECAP rig were designated as discrete and rigid whereas the billet, a rectangular bar of dimension 19.5 by 19.5 by 60 mm was designated as discrete and deformable. The software facilitated the creation of a detailed die design to achieve the desired material deformation behavior.

- Material Selection

Material properties were analyzed for the plunger, die and extrusion rig cover. The key factors taken into consideration in the selection of suitable materials is its compatibility with the sample and required material strength. Tool steel was assigned to the extrusion rig and plunger. 5083 type Al-mg alloy was assigned to the sample.

A suitable Mesh size was applied to the Extrusion rig after which the assembly module was selected and the parts assembled together. Von mises stress criterion was conducted on the die and results obtained.

C. Fabrication of Experimental ECAP Rig

This section details the post-design steps employed during fabrication of the experimental ECAP extrusion rig.

- Material procurement and machining

Following the design work on Autodesk inventor software, the next phase involved the procurement of thick-walled tool steel material. The dimensions as per the inventor design were strictly adhered to. The tool steel was machined precisely to replicate the dimensions and designs for the plunger, extrusion rig and die as developed in the Autodesk inventor software. This machining process aimed to ensure an exact match between the virtual design and the physical components.

- Die Surface Polishing

After machining, the die was subjected to a polishing procedure to achieve smooth finishing so as to minimize friction and wear during the ECAP process thereby enhancing the uniformity and quality of the extruded material.

Experimental Procedure

The experimental procedures including the preparation of billets, ECAP process at varying temperatures and assembly of the extrusion rig is outlined as follows;

- Billet Preparation

The billets (al-mg alloy) were thoroughly cleaned to remove any impurity that could impact the experimental results after which each billet was labelled for easy identification during the experimental process.

- ECAP Processing

The extrusion rig was employed to subject the billets to severe plastic deformation. Four ECAP passes were performed at varying temperatures of 90, 100, 120, 140 and 150 °C respectively. This temperature variations were part of the experimental design to investigate temperature-dependent behavior of the material.

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Figure 2: Experimental set up for extrusion of billets

- Assembly and Heating

The extrusion rig was cleaned and lubricant (Molybdenum disulfide MoS_2) was applied to the die. The rig was assembled ensuring a secure and sealed environment for the ECAP process. The heating elements and thermostat were inserted into their respective housings in the rig and connected to a power source (see figure 2). This is to regulate the temperature of the billet during the ECAP process ensuring the specified temperatures, 90, 100, 120, 140 and 150 °C was maintained. The extrusion chamber was preheated for first temperature and lubricated billets loaded into the die. This was repeated for all temperatures.

During the ECAP process, data collection and monitoring were conducted to record the temperature, pressure and nature of deformation observed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of stress analysis obtained after simulation for the die are shown in Figures 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 respectively.

Figure 3: ECAP die Von Mises Stress report

The results of stress analysis of the ECAP die using von mises criterion as presented revealed a maximum stress of 170.722 Mpa will be induced into the die as a result of sample deformation (Figure 3). This value is however, lower than the die material yield stress 700 MPa indicating the design is safe where no die fracture due to generated residual stress during ECAP processing exist. This finding is in agreement with Reham (2019) [12]. The minimum Von Mises stress observed was 0.264388 MPa. This shows areas with relatively low stress levels. The 1st principal stress (maximum tensile stress) induced on the ECAP die is 173.023 Mpa while the 3rd principal stress (maximum compressive strength) induced on the die is 38.3494 Mpa (Figure 4).

The result showed that a maximum factor of safety of 15 and a minimum value of 1.21 will be induced which indicates the die is safe for implementation (Figure 7a). Figure 5 and 6 respectively gives information about the strain suffered by the model where the red region represents the largest strain suffered. The strain values were all very small demonstrating the possible integrity of the model.

Figure 4: (a) first and (b) third principal stress report

Figure 5: Equivalent Strain for ECAP die

Figure 6: (a) first and (b) third principal strain

Figure 7: (a) Displacement and (b) factor of safety report for ECAP die

The amount of pressing pressure applied during experimental extrusion process at varied temperature and number of passes is shown in figure 8.

The result of the laboratory experiment shed light on the crucial relationship between temperature and pressing pressure and the number of passes employed. The result showed an increase in pressing pressure as the number of ECAP passes increased at 90 °C (figure 8a). This trend was consistent with our observations at 100 °C where the pressing pressure also rose with additional passes. This is because as the al-mg alloy undergoes repeated deformation passes through the ECAP die, work hardening occurs. Work hardening results in an increase in materials flow stress requiring higher pressures to induce further plastic deformation (Muhammad et al., 2017). Furthermore, with each pass, the material becomes harder and more resistant to deformation necessitating an increase in pressure to maintain plastic flow. As the number of passes increases, grain size reduction becomes more challenging requiring higher pressures to induce additional deformation and grain refinement.

The result for temperatures 120, 140 and 150 °C showed a more gradual increase in pressing pressure with increase in number of passes. This can be attributed to the effect of temperature in terms of energy utilization and pressing pressure. However, the result showed a decrease in pressing pressure with increase in temperature (see Figure 8b). This could be attributed to several factors such as softening of the material as a result of temperature increase thereby requiring less pressing pressure to deform during the ECAP process. Also, higher temperatures can lead to reduced friction between the materials and die, allowing for easier deformation and requiring less pressure which is in agreement with Thiyaneshwaran *et al.*, (2013) [3]. From figure 8a, a negative linear trend was observed between temperature and pressing pressure for all passes. The linear trend is characterized by the equation $Y = -m(x) + b$ where Y represents the independent variable (pressing pressure), x represents the independent variable (temperature), m is the slope of the line which is the rate of change of (Y) with respect to (x) and b is the y-intercept, indicating the value of (y) when (x) is zero. This behavior is however, typical in many metals forming processes where elevated temperature enhances material ductility and reduce flow stress thereby lowering the pressing pressure needed to achieve deformation. Figure 8b showed a positive linear trend in pressure against the number of passes. This trend indicates as the material undergoes multiple passes through the die, the pressing pressure tends to increase. This could be attributed to the cumulative effect of strain hardening and material refinement with each pass. As the number of passes increase, the material becomes increasingly resistant to deformation. Therefore, higher pressures are required to achieve further plastic flow. These trends provide valuable data for developing predictive models of the ECAP extrusion process.

Figure 5: Pressing pressure on Al-mg Alloy during ECAP

CONCLUSION

ECAP extrusion rig was developed and successfully implemented at various temperatures. The investigation of the rig's performance using Al-mg alloy in the laboratory revealed significant insights into the materials behavior under severe plastic deformation. In addition, the practical implications of our findings are significant as the choice of temperature for ECAP process can directly impact the energy efficiency of extrusion as well as the quality of resulting material. This information can guide industrial process and applications enabling a more energy-efficient and effective material refinement.

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